

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
HOTEL BILLING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
REPORT
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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Hotel Billing Systems Billing is a financial accounting concept for business organizations such as hotel industry to bill their customers for services rendered and the billing report is utilized by management to know the income generated. Hotel billing record system is used to capture the bill record of customers to come up with a total amount to be paid by the customer. The information is saved to a database to enable management or users to retrieve saved billing records. The service rendered by hotel industry are associated with charges. It is therefore pertinent that accurate billing of the service rendered is properly documented. The application of the computer system to aid business transaction is very significant. This is because the computer system provides features such as storage, computation, easy retrieval of information etc. in addition; the computer system is very fast and accurate as against manual systems of recording and retrieving information. Virtually all organizations are now shifting from their manual systems to computerized systems as a result of the benefits it presents. Hotel industries are among the league of organization that can make use of the computer system and software solution to manage their billing records. The manual billing system is time consuming: It takes time to compute the bill of customers in the existing system due to the manual process being used. Human error due to miscalculations: Miscalculations can occur as a result of human error. It is difficult to easily manage and update billing information: If there is need to correct a billing record or make changes, it will be difficult to instantly find and update the bill record of the particular customer.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

The aim of the study is to develop a billing system for hotel industry. This will aid in the computation of customers billing information pertaining to hotel services offered so that billing reports can be presented when needed. The following are the objectives to facilitate the stated To design a system to compute billing information of customers of the hotel industry. To design a system that can be used to store customers billing records. To implement a system that can be used to retrieve and update customer billing records easily. To enable the user to look up his/her confirmed reservation or modify or cancel the reservation if required. 3. To allow the manager of the hotel to enlist his hotel with the system .To allows the manager of the hotel to scrutinize the list of orders and their details.

CHAPTER 2

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing manual system a lot of time is spent in communicating the information across different branches. There is a need for an integrated automated system, which has some centralized control over the entire process. Conventional System makes use of huge amounts of paper for recording transactions. The existing system is a manually maintained system. All the Hotel records are to be maintained for the details of each customer, Fee details, Room Allocation, Attendance. All these details are entered and retrieved manually.

DISADVANTAGES:

1. Time Consuming.
2. Updating process.
3. Inaccuracy of data.

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Proposed system the computerized version of the existing system. Provides easy and quick access over the data. Keeping records of admission of Resident Properly so that facilities provided by Hotels are fully utilized in effective and efficient manner. Keeping the records of salary structure of the workers of Hotel by billing approach.

ADVANTAGES:

1. Storing resident details correctly.
2. Maintain accuracy.

2.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY:

All projects are feasible given unlimited resources and infinite time. It is both necessary and prudent to evaluate the feasibility of the project at the earliest possible time. Feasibility and risk analysis is related in many ways. If project risk is great, the feasibility listed below is equally important.

The following feasibility technique has been used in this project:

- Operational Feasibility
- Technical Feasibility
- Economic Feasibility

2.3.1 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY:

The approach used to solve the two proposed tasks is based on NLP and ML techniques. In a standard supervised ML setting, a training set and a test set are required. The training set is used to train the ML algorithm and the test set to test its performance. The objectives are to build models that can later be deployed on other test sets with high performance.

2.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY:

One of the major contributions of this work is the fact that the current experiments show that additional information in the representation settings brings improvements for the task of identifying informative sentences. The task itself is a knowledge-charged task; the labeling process involves a human-intensive annotation process since relations between entities need to be manually identified.

The experiments designed for the automatic task aim to show that classifiers perform better when richer information is provided.

2.3.2 Economic Feasibility:

A system can be developed technically and that will be used if installed must still be a good investment for the organization. In the economical feasibility, the development cost in creating the system is evaluated against the ultimate benefit derived from the new systems. Financial benefits must equal or exceed the costs. The system is economically feasible. It does not require any addition hardware or software. This product is more feasible in technical part. Though it is more software based many of the physical requirements are avoided and cost also avoided for the physical requirements

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

3.3.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Processor : Dual core processor 2.6.0 GHz
- RAM : 1GB
- Hard disk : 160 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 MB
- Keyboard : Standard keyboard
- Monitor : 15 inch color monitor

3.3.2 SOFTWARE SPECIFICATION

- Front End : PHP
- IDE : dream weaver
- Back End : My SQL

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

4.1 FRONT END (PHP):

4.1.3 PHP

PHP is server side back end programming language. It executes in server along with maximum all available web servers like Apache, IIS (Internet Information Server) etc., and return the response as required MIME type. It is a Pre Process Hypertext; we could do many things on server by using PHP on server and co-ordinate with DB server for CURD (Create, Update, Read, and Delete) actions. Front end in the séance, UI which intact the users, it can done by HTML, or any others. And UI Behavior is defined in UI back end Languages (Scripting languages) via: Java script, VB script

PHP started out as a small open source project that evolved as more and more people found out how useful it was. Rasmus Leadoff unleashed the first version of PHP way back in 1994.

- PHP is a recursive acronym for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor".
- PHP is a server side scripting language that is embedded in HTML. It is used to manage dynamic content, databases, session tracking, even build entire e-commerce sites.
- It is integrated with a number of popular databases, including MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, Sybase, Informix, and Microsoft SQL Server.
- PHP is pleasingly zippy in its execution, especially when compiled as an Apache module on the UNIX side. The MySQL server, once started, executes even very complex queries with huge result sets in record-setting time.
- PHP supports a large number of major protocols such as POP3, IMAP, and LDAP. PHP4 added support for Java and distributed object architectures (COM and CORBA), making n-tier development a possibility for the first time.
- PHP is forgiving: PHP language tries to be as forgiving as possible.

- PHP Syntax is C-Like.

Common Uses of PHP

PHP performs system functions, i.e. from files on a system it can create, open, read, write and close them. The other uses of PHP are:

PHP can handle forms, i.e. gather data from files, save data to a file, thru email you can send data, return data to the user. You add, delete and modify elements within your database thru PHP. Access cookies variables and set cookies. Using PHP, you can restrict users to access some pages of your website. It can encrypt data.

Characteristics of PHP

Five important characteristics make PHP's practical nature possible:

- Simplicity
- Efficiency
- Security
- Flexibility
- Familiarity

PHP Variables

The main way to store information in the middle of a PHP program is by using a variable. Here are the most important things to know about variables in PHP.

- All variables in PHP are denoted with a leading dollar sign (\$).
- The value of a variable is the value of its most recent assignment.
- Variables are assigned with the = operator, with the variable on the left-hand side and the expression to be evaluated on the right.
- Variables can, but do not need, to be declared before assignment.
- Variables in PHP do not have intrinsic types - a variable does not know in advance whether it will be used to store a number or a string of characters.
- Variables used before they are assigned have default values.
- PHP does a good job of automatically converting types from one to another when necessary.

PHP variables are Perl-like. PHP has a total of eight data types which we use to construct our variables:

- **Integers:** are whole numbers, without a decimal point, like 4195.
- **Doubles:** are floating-point numbers, like 3.14159 or 49.1.
- **Booleans:** have only two possible values either true or false.
- **NULL:** is a special type that only has one value: NULL.
- **Strings:** are sequences of characters, like 'PHP supports string operations.'
- **Arrays:** are named and indexed collections of other values.
- **Objects:** are instances of programmer-defined classes, which can package up both other kinds of values and functions that are specific to the class.
- **Resources:** are special variables that hold references to resources external to PHP (such as database connections).

Back End (MySQL)

MySQL is the world's most used open source relational database management system (RDBMS) as of 2008 that run as a server providing multi-user access to a number of databases. The MySQL development project has made its source code available under the terms of the GNU General Public License, as well as under a variety of proprietary agreements. MySQL was owned and sponsored by a single for-profit firm, the Swedish company MySQL AB, now owned by Oracle Corporation.

MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack—LAMP is an acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/PHP/Python." Free-software-open source projects that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

For commercial use, several paid editions are available, and offer additional functionality. Applications which use MySQL databases include: TYPO3, Joomla, Word Press, phpBB, MyBB, Drupal and other software built on the LAMP software stack. MySQL is also used in many high-profile, large-scale World Wide Web products, including Wikipedia, Google (though not for searches), ImagebookTwitter, Flickr, Nokia.com, and YouTube.

Inter images

MySQL is primarily an RDBMS and ships with no GUI tools to administer MySQL databases or manage data contained within the databases. Users may use the included command line tools, or use MySQL "front-ends", desktop software and web applications that create and manage MySQL databases, build database structures, back up data, inspect status, and work with data records. The official set of MySQL front-end tools, MySQL Workbench is actively developed by Oracle, and is freely available for use.

Graphical

The official MySQL Workbench is a free integrated environment developed by MySQL AB, which enables users to graphically administer MySQL databases and visually design database structures. MySQL Workbench replaces the previous package of software, MySQL GUI Tools. Similar to other third-party packages, but still considered the authoritative MySQL frontend, MySQL Workbench lets users manage database design & modeling, SQL development (replacing MySQL Query Browser) and Database administration (replacing MySQL Administrator). MySQL Workbench is available in two editions, the regular free and open source Community Edition which may be downloaded from the MySQL website, and the proprietary Standard Edition which extends and improves the feature set of the Community Edition.

MySQL ships with some command line tools. Third-parties have also developed tools to manage a MySQL server, some listed below. Maatkit - a cross-platform toolkit for MySQL, PostgreSQL and Memcached, developed in Perl Maatkit can be used to prove replication is working correctly, fix corrupted data, automate repetitive tasks, and speed up servers. Maatkit is included with several GNU/Linux distributions such as CentOS and Debian and packages are available for Programming. MySQL works on many different system platforms, including AIX, BSDi, FreeBSD, HP-UX, eComStation, i5/OS, IRIX, Linux, Mac OS X, Microsoft Windows, NetBSD, Novell NetWare, OpenBSD, OpenSolaris, OS/2 Warp, QNX, Solaris, Symbian, SunOS, SCO Open Server, SCO UnixWare, Sanos and Tru64. A port of MySQL to OpenVMS also exists. MySQL is written in C and C++. Its SQL parser is written in yacc, and a home-brewed lexical analyzer. Many programming languages with language-specific APIs include libraries for accessing MySQL databases. These include MySQL Connector/Net for integration with Microsoft's Visual Studio (languages such as C# and VB are most commonly used) and the JDBC

driver for Java. In addition, an ODBCinterimage called MyODBC allows additional programming languages that support the ODBC inter image to communicate with a MySQL database, such as ASP or ColdFusion. The HTSQL - URL-based query method also ships with a MySQL adapter, allowing direct interaction between a MySQL database and any web client via structured URLs

Features

As of April 2009, MySQL offered MySQL 5.1 in two different variants: the open source MySQL Community Server and the commercial Enterprise Server. MySQL 5.5 is offered under the same licenses. They have a common code base and include the following features:

A broad subset of ANSI SQL 99, as well as extensions

- Cross-platform support
- Stored procedures
- Triggers
- Cursors
- Updatable Views
- Information schema

Strict mode (ensures MySQL does not truncate or otherwise modify data to conform to an underlying data type, when an incompatible value is inserted into that type)

X/Open XAdistributed transaction processing (DTP) support; two phase commit as part of this, using Oracle's InnoDB engine

- Transactions with the InnoDB, and Cluster storage engines
- SSL support
- Query caching
- Sub-SELECTs (i.e. nested SELECTs)
- Replication support (i.e. Master-Master Replication & Master-Slave Replication)
- Embedded database library
- Partitioned tables with pruning of partitions in optimizer

- Shared-nothing clustering through MySQL Cluster
- Hot backup (via mysqlhotcopy) under certain conditions

Multiple storage engines, allowing one to choose the one that is most effective for each table in the application (in MySQL 5.0, storage engines must be compiled in; in MySQL 5.1, storage engines can be dynamically loaded at run time): Native storage engines (MyISAM, Falcon, Merge, Memory (heap), Federated, Archive, CSV, Black hole, Cluster, EXAMPLE, Maria, and InnoDB, which was made the default as of 5.5). Partner-developed storage engines (solidDB, NitroEDB, ScaleDB, TokuDB, Infobright (formerly Brighthouse), Kickfire, XtraDB, IBM DB2). InnoDB used to be a partner-developed storage engine, but with recent acquisitions, Oracle now owns both MySQL core and InnoDB.

CHAPTER 5

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

5.1 PROBLEM DEFINITION:

A hotel system manages information about rooms, reservations, customers, and customer billing. A customer can make reservations, change, or cancel reservations through the hotel website. When a customer makes reservations, he/she needs to check if a room the customer wants to reserve is available. If a room is available, the customer enters his/her information to the system and receives a confirmation number from the web site.

A desk clerk checks in a customer with only a prior reservation, change the checkout date, and check out the customer. A room is assigned to the customer at check-in time and a customer billing record is created at that time. The customer billing record is updated every night at 12. When a customer checks out, the desk clerk prints the bill. A customer can pay by cash, check, or credit card when he/she checks out.

The manual billing system is time consuming: It takes time to compute the bill of customers in Human error due to miscalculations: Miscalculations can occur as a result of human error such as It is difficult to easily manage and update billing information: If there is need to correct a billing record or make changes, it will be difficult to instantly find and update the bill record of the particular customer.

Billing the activity of charging a client for goods and services rendered. Accounting the activity, practice, or profession of maintaining the business records of a person or organization. System a combination of components working together to achieve a particular goal. Software programs and applications that can be run on a computer system .Management the organizing and controlling of the affairs of a business or sector of a business. Hotel An establishment that provide accommodation and other services for paying guests.

5.2 OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT:

The aim of the study is to develop a billing system for hotel industry. This will aid in the computation of customers billing information pertaining to hotel services offered so that billing reports can be presented when needed. To design a system to compute billing information of custom to implement a system that can be used to retrieve and update customer billing records easily.

5.3 MODULE DESCRIPTION

5.3.1 Input progression

MODULES

- **ADMIN**
- **CUSTOMER**
- **BILLING AND PAYMENT**

ADMIN

Admin is the first and main module in this application. Admin is the responsible person for adding and updating the dish menu and dish prices. Admin can add the data and also he can view the food details.

CUSTOMER

Customer will be provided with a separate login session so that they have to login with their username and password to order the food and view the price details.

BILLING AND PAYMENT

Food, food prices, pending bill and related all kind of reports and features of **hotel** billing website application.

5.3 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

**5.5 UML DIAGRAMS:
USECASE DIAGRAM:**

CLASS DIAGRAM:

Class Diagram for Hotel Management System

SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

5.4 DATABASE DESIGN:

5.6.1 Table 1:

Database php_hotel_billing

Table structure for table food_details

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
food_name	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
food_type	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
price	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
fname	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
report	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table food_details

1	idly	Veg	50	aa.jpg	0	0
---	------	-----	----	--------	---	---

Table structure for table order_details

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(100)	Yes	NULL
uname	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
fid	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
fname	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
report	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table order_details

3	arun	1	idly	1	50
4	arun	1	idly	1	50

Table structure for table user_details

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
name	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
gender	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
emailid	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
mobile	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
address	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
username	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
passsword	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_details

1	arun	Male	arun@gmail.com	7339333830	trichy	arun	123
---	------	------	----------------	------------	--------	------	-----

Table structure for table user_payment

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(100)	Yes	NULL
username	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
amount	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
holder	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
card	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
ccv	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
exdate	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_payment

1	arun	100	arun	654564564541	455	2020-01-16	0
---	------	-----	------	--------------	-----	------------	---

5.5 INPUT DESIGN:

Input Design is the process of converting a user-oriented description of the input into a computer-based system. This design is important to avoid errors in the data input process and show the correct direction to the management for getting correct information from the computerized system. To keep the screen simple by giving proper sequence, information, and clear captions. To meet the intended purpose by using appropriate forms. To ensure the completion of form with accuracy.

5.6 OUTPUT DESIGN:

Output Design a quality output is one, which meets the requirements of the end user and presents the information clearly. In any system results of processing are communicated to the users and to other system through outputs..Create document, report, or other formats that contain information produced by the system.

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM TESTING

Testing Definitions

Software development has several levels of testing.

- Unit Testing
- Systems Testing
- Acceptance Testing

6.1 UNIT TESTING:

The first level of testing is called unit testing which is done during the development of the system. Unit testing is essential for verification of the code produced during the coding phase. Errors were been noted down and corrected immediately. It is performed by the programmer. It uses the program specifications and the program itself as its source. Thus, our modules are individually tested here. There is no formal documentation required for unit-testing program.

6.2 ACCEPTANCE TESTING:

The final level of testing is the acceptance testing. Acceptance testing provides the users with assurance that the system is ready for production use; it is performed by the users. It uses the System Requirements document as its source. There is no formal documentation required for acceptance testing.

Systems testing are the major testing effort of the project. It is the functional testing of the application and is concerned with following,

- Quality/standards compliance
- Business requirements
- Performance capabilities
- Operational capabilities

Below are defined a few test cases which have been implemented for the various screens. The outputs have been registered and the required changes have been incorporated.

6.3 TEST CASES:

A *test case* is a detailed procedure that fully tests a feature or an aspect of a feature. Whereas the test plan describes what to test, a test case describes how to perform a particular test.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

This work is carried out to identify and discuss the need for a computer system in hotel business billing system. A hotel business is a hospitality industry which caters for both leisure and well being of its guest. The duties of hotels are to offer accommodation to their guest and to render services to them. These services are usually personal.

The focus on this topic is to introduce computer in the allocation of rooms and billing system of a hotel. The current process of billing is being operated manually and due to this procedure numerous problem are been encountered.

A design was taken computerized the manual process in order to check this problem. The problems were identified after series of interviews and examination of documents after which analysis was made and a computerized procedure recommended. This project will also suggest how to successfully implement the computerized procedure and to overcome the obstacle that would hinder the successful implementation of the system. The new system was designed using Microsoft visual basic 6.0 programming language. This language was chosen because of its easy syntax and features for developing windows based applications.

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A customer's web browser issues an HTTP request from the Contact page. On clicking the button, the content of the fields are posted from the customer's browser as a request to the web server. On receiving the request, the web server retrieves the file, Contacts.asp from its disk or memory and passes it to the , php.dll, after processing the file php sends the HTML page to the server.

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

8.1 CONCLUSION:

The Online Hotel Billing System was developed to replace the manual process of booking for a hotel room or any other facility of the hotel. The old system does not serve the customer in a better way; rather it makes customer data vulnerable. The new system keeps proper records of customers for emergency and security purposes. The hotel's advertising effort is now accompanied by a virtual tour created on the system. Thus, we present an automated food ordering system with features of feedback and wireless communication. This system is convenient, effective and easy thereby improving the performance of restaurant's staff. This System also ensures good quality of service and customer satisfaction. Thus, the proposed system has the potential to attract customers and also adds to the Efficiency of maintaining the restaurant's ordering and Billing sections.

8.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS:

As the current system is a file based one, management of the hotel has to put much effort on securing those files. They can be easily get damaged by a fire, insects or even by a natural disaster like tsunami. Keeping files takes much time and wastes much precious man hours. Although we can't trust the accuracy of calculations done by manually, it's not a surprise of encountering problems. If we want to check for a previous room record or a reservation detail, management will be in a great problem. It's a tough and time taking process to search for a toimplementwillbecoveringallthebasic processes done in the Hotel. It would handle Guest details, Reservation details, Inventory management details, Room service details, staff management details and room types.

CHAPTER 9

APPENDIX

9.1 SOURCE CODE

ADMIN

```
<?php
session_start();
include("dbconnect.php");
extract($_POST);
if(isset($_Submit))
{
if(($_user=="admin") && ($_password=="admin"))
{
?>

<script language="javascript">
alert("Successfully..");
window.location.href="admin_home.php";
</script>
<?php
}else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Username Password is wrong..");
window.location.href="admin.php";
</script>
<?php

}
}
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
```

```

<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion" rel="stylesheet"
type="text/css">
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic" rel="stylesheet"
type="text/css">
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed"
rel="stylesheet" type="text/css">
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                        <div class="navbar-header">
                            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
                                <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                            </button>
                            <div class="navbar-brand">
                                <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
                            </div>
                        </div>
                    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
                        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
                            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
                                <li ><a href="index.php">Home
<span class="sr-only">(current)</span></a></li>
                                <li class="active"><a
href="admin.php">Admin</a></li>

```

```

                <li><a
href="customer.php">Customer</a></li>
                </ul>

                </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
            </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
        </nav>

    </div>
</div>
<!--header-->
    <!--content-->
        <div class="content">
            <div class="contact">
                <div class="container">
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>Admin Login </h2>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                        <table width="33%"
height="142" border="0" align="center">
                            <tr>
                                <td width="29%">username</td>
                                <td width="71%"><label>
                                    <input name="user" type="text"
id="user" required="">
                                </label></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td>password</td>
                                <td><label>
                                    <input name="password"
type="password" id="password" required="">
                                </label></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td><label>
                                    <input type="submit" name="Submit"
value="Submit">
                                </label></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td><a
href="user_registration.php"></a></td>
                            </tr>
                        </table>

```

```

                </form>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <div class="contact-grids">
                    <div class="clearfix"></div>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="footer-section">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="footer-grids">
                <div class="clearfix"></div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--footer-->

    </div>
    <!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
            <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
    </div>
    <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>

```

```

ADD FOOD <?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

if(isset($_POST['Submit']))
{
// $fileName = $_FILES['file']['name'];
$name=$_FILES['file']['name'];
$tmpFileName = $_FILES['file']['tmp_name'];
$error = $_FILES['file']['error'];
$contentType = $_FILES['file']['type'];
$fileSize = $_FILES['file']['size'];
move_uploaded_file($_FILES['file']['tmp_name'], "upload/".$name);

$max_qry = mysql_query("select max(id) from food_details");
$max_row = mysql_fetch_array($max_qry);
$id=$max_row['max(id)']+1;

```

```

        $qry=mysql_query("insert into food_details
values ('$id', '$fn', '$ftype', '$price', '$fname', '0', '0')");
if($qry)
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
    alert("Product will be added Successfully..");
    window.location.href="admin_add_food.php";
</script>
    <?php
}
else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Failed..");
window.location.href="admin_add_food.php";
</script>
    <?php

}
}
?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion" rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic" rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>

```

```

<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style1 {color: #004000}
.style2 {color: #337AB7; }
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                        <div class="navbar-header">
                            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
                                <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                </button>
                                <div class="navbar-brand">
                                    <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
                                        </div>
                                    </div>
                                </div>
                    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
                        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
                            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
                                <li ><a
href="admin_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
                                    <li class="active" ><a
href="admin_add_food.php">Add Food</a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="admin_food_details.php">Food Details</a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="admin_customers.php">Customers</a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="admin_order.php">Order</a></li>

```

```

                <li ><a
href="admin_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
                <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
            </ul>

        </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
    </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
</nav>

</div>
</div>
<!--header-->
    <!--content-->
        <div class="content">
            <div class="contact">
                <div class="container">
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>Add Food Details </h2>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <form action="" method="post"
enctype="multipart/form-data" name="form1">
                        <table width="618"
height="189" border="0" align="center">
                            <tr>
                                <td width="285"><h3 align="right"
class="style2">Food Name </h3></td>
                                <td width="33">&nbsp;</td>
                                <td width="286"><div align="left">
                                    <input name="fn" type="text"
id="fn" required="">
                                </div></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td><h3 align="right"
class="style2">Type</h3></td>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td><div align="left">
                                    <select name="ftype" id="ftype">
                                        <option value="Veg">Veg</option>
                                        <option value="Non veg">Non
veg</option>
                                    </select>
                                </div></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td><h3 align="right"
class="style2">Price</h3></td>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>

```

```

        <td><div align="left">
            <input name="price" type="text"
id="price" required="">
        </div></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td><h3 align="right"
class="style2">Image</h3></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><div align="left">
            <input type="file" name="file"
required="">
        </div></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td><h3><span
class="style1"></span></h3></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><div align="left">
            <input type="submit" name="Submit"
value="Update">
        </div></td>
    </tr>
</table>
</form>
    <p>&nbsp;</p>
    <p>&nbsp;</p>
    <div class="contact-grids">
        <div class="clearfix"></div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
    <div class="footer-section">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="footer-grids">
                <div class="clearfix"></div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--footer-->

</div>
<!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
            <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--copy-->
</body>

```

```

</html>
VIEW CUSTOMERS
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link
href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style12 {color: #000000; font-weight: bold; font-size: 18px; }
.style29 {font-size: 16px; color:#008000; font-weight: bold; }
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                                <div class="navbar-header">

```

```

        <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
        <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
    </button>
    <div class="navbar-brand">
        <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
    </div>
</div>

    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
    <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
        <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
            <li ><a
href="admin_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
            <li ><a
href="admin_add_food.php">Add Food</a></li>
            <li ><a
href="admin_food_details.php">Food Details</a></li>
            <li class="active"><a
href="admin_customers.php">Customers</a></li>
            <li ><a
href="admin_order.php">Order</a></li>
            <li ><a
href="admin_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
            <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
        </ul>
    </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
</div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
</nav>

</div>
</div>
<!--header-->
    <!--content-->
    <div class="content">
        <div class="contact">
            <div class="container">
                <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

```

```

                <h2>Customer Details </h2>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                <table width="100%"
border="0">
                    <tr>
                        <th width="10%" height="55"
class="style12" scope="col"><div align="center">Id</div></th>
                        <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Name</div></th>
                        <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Gender</div></th>
                        <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Email Id</div></th>
                        <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Mobile</div></th>
                        <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Address</div></th>
                    </tr>
                    <?php
                    $qry=mysql_query("select * from user_details");
                    while($row=mysql_fetch_array($qry))
                    {
                    ?>
                        <tr>
                            <td height="38"><div
align="center"><span class="style29"><?php echo
$row['id'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['name'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['gender'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['emailid'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['mobile'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['address'];?></span></div></td>
                        </tr>
                        <?php
                    }
                    ?>
                </table>
                </form>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                <div class="contact-grids">
                    <div class="clearfix"></div>
                </div>
            </div>

```

```

        </div>

        <div class="footer-section">
            <div class="container">
                <div class="footer-grids">
                    <div class="clearfix"></div>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    <!--footer-->

    </div>
    <!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
            <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
    </div>
    <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>

```

ADD ORDERS

```

<?php
include("dbconnect.php");

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>

```

```

<link
href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style12 {color: #000000; font-weight: bold; font-size: 18px; }
.style29 {font-size: 16px; color:#008000; font-weight: bold; }
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                        <div class="navbar-header">
                            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
                                <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                </button>
                                <div class="navbar-brand">
                                    <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
                                        </div>
                                    </div>
                                </div>
                    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
                        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
                            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
                                <li ><a
href="admin_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="admin_add_food.php">Add Food</a></li>
                                    <li class="active"><a
href="admin_food_details.php">Food Details</a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="admin_customers.php">Customers</a></li>

```

```

                                <li ><a
href="admin_order.php">Order</a></li>

                                <li ><a
href="admin_payment.php">Payment</a></li>

                                <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
                                </ul>

                                </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
                                </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
                                </nav>

                                </div>
                                </div>
<!--header-->
                                <!--content-->
                                <div class="content">
                                    <div class="contact">
                                        <div class="container">
                                            <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                                            <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                                            <h2>Food Details </h2>
                                            <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                            <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                            <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                                                <table width="100%"
border="0">
                                                    <tr>
                                                        <th width="10%" height="55"
class="style12" scope="col"><div align="center">Id</div></th>
                                                        <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Food Name</div></th>
                                                        <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Category</div></th>
                                                        <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Quantity</div></th>
                                                        <th width="15%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Image</div></th>
                                                    </tr>
                                                    <?php
                                                        $qry=mysql_query("select * from food_details");
                                                        while($row=mysql_fetch_array($qry))
                                                        {
                                                            ?>
                                                                <tr>
                                                                    <td height="38"><div
align="center"><span class="style29"><?php echo
$row['id'];?></span></div></td>

```

```

                <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['food_name'];?></span></div></td>
                <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['food_type'];?></span></div></td>
                <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['price'];?></span></div></td>
                <td></td>
            </tr>
            <?php
        }
    ?>
        </table>
        </form>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <div class="contact-grids">
            <div class="clearfix"></div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

    <div class="footer-section">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="footer-grids">
                <div class="clearfix"></div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--footer-->

</div>
<!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
            <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--copy-->
</body>
</html>

```

USER REGISTRATION

```

<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$username=$_SESSION['un'];

```

```

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion" rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic" rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed"
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style12 {color: #000000; font-weight: bold; font-size: 18px; }
.style29 {font-size: 16px; color:#008000; font-weight: bold; }
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
<div class="header head-top">
<div class="container">
<nav class="navbar navbar-default">
<div class="container-fluid">
<!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
<div class="navbar-header">
<button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
<span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>

```

```

        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
    </button>
    <div class="navbar-brand">
        <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
    </div>
</div>

    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
    toggling -->
        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
                <li class="active" ><a
href="user_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
                <li ><a
href="user_order_food.php">Order Food</a></li>
                <li ><a
href="user_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
                <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
            </ul>

        </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
    </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
</nav>

</div>
</div>
<!--header-->
    <!--content-->
        <div class="content">
            <div class="contact">
                <div class="container">
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>Food Details </h2>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                        <table width="100%"
border="0">
                            <tr>
                                <th width="10%" height="55"
class="style12" scope="col"><div align="center">Id</div></th>
                                <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Food</div></th>

```

```

                <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Food ID</div></th>
                <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Price</div></th>
            </tr>
            <?php
                $qry=mysql_query("select * from order_details where
uname='$uname' and status=1");
                while($row=mysql_fetch_array($qry))
                {
                    ?>
                        <tr>
                            <td height="38"><div
align="center"><span class="style29"><?php echo
$row['id'];?></span></div></td>
                                <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['fname'];?></span></div></td>
                                    <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['fid'];?></span></div></td>
                                        <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['report'];?></span></div></td>
                                            </tr>
                                                <?php
                                                    }
                                                        ?>
                                                            </table>
                                                                </form>
                                                                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                                                        <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                                                            <div class="contact-grids">
                                                                                <div class="clearfix"></div>
                                                                                    </div>
                                                                                        </div>
                                                                                            </div>
                                                                                                </div>
                                                                                                    <!--footer-->
                                                                                                        </div>
                                                                                                            <!--copy-->
                                                                                                                <div class="copy-section">
                                                                                                                    <div class="container">
                                                                                                                        <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
                                                                                                                            </div>
                                                                                                                                </div>
                                                                                                                                    </div>

```

```
                                <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>
```

FOOD ORDER

```
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link
href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style12 {color: #000000; font-weight: bold; font-size: 18px; }
.style29 {font-size: 16px; color:#008000; font-weight: bold; }
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
```

```

        <div class="container-fluid">
      <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
          <div class="navbar-header">
            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
              <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
              <span class="icon-bar"></span>
              <span class="icon-bar"></span>
              <span class="icon-bar"></span>
            </button>
            <div class="navbar-brand">
              <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
            </div>
          </div>

      <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
          <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
              <li ><a
href="user_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
              <li class="active" ><a
href="user_order_food.php">Order Food</a></li>
              <li ><a
href="user_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
              <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
            </ul>

          </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
        </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
      </nav>

    </div>
  </div>
<!--header-->
  <!--content-->
    <div class="content">
      <div class="contact">
        <div class="container">
          <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
          <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
          <h2>Food Order</h2>
          <p>&nbsp;</p>
          <p>&nbsp;</p>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>

```

```

        <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
        <table width="100%"
border="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="10%" height="55"
class="style12" scope="col"><div align="center">Id</div></th>
                <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Food Name</div></th>
                <th width="11%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Category</div></th>
                <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Quantity</div></th>
                <th width="15%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Image</div></th>
                <th width="13%" class="style12"
scope="col"><div align="center">Order</div></th>
            </tr>
            <?php
                $qry=mysql_query("select * from food_details");
                while($row=mysql_fetch_array($qry))
                {
                    ?>
                    <tr>
                        <td height="38"><div
align="center"><span class="style29"><?php echo
$row['id'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['food_name'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['food_type'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td><div align="center"><span
class="style29"><?php echo $row['price'];?></span></div></td>
                            <td></td>
                            <td><a
href="user_order_food_1.php?id=<?php echo $row['id'];?>&f=<?php echo
$row['food_name'];?>&p=<?php echo $row['price'];?>">select</a></td>
                        </tr>
                    <?php
                }
            ?>
        </table>
        </form>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <div class="contact-grids">
            <div class="clearfix"></div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

```

```

        <div class="footer-section">
            <div class="container">
                <div class="footer-grids">
                    <div class="clearfix"></div>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    <!--footer-->

    </div>
    <!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
            <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
    </div>
    <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>

<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);
$username=$_SESSION['un'];
    $total=0;
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from order_details where unname='$username' and
status=0");
if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$fit=$_REQUEST['t'];
header("Location:user_payment_1.php?f=".$fit);

}

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,

```

```

Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion" rel="stylesheet"
type='text/css'>
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic" rel="stylesheet"
type='text/css'>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed"
rel="stylesheet" type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style1 {color: #004080}
.style2 {color: #B35900}
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                        <div class="navbar-header">
                            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
                                <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                            </button>
                            <div class="navbar-brand">
                                <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
                            </div>
                        </div>
                    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
                        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
                            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">

```

```

                                <li ><a
href="user_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
                                <li ><a
href="user_order_food.php">Order Food</a></li>
                                <li class="active"><a
href="user_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
                                <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
                                </ul>

                                </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
                                </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
                                </nav>

                                </div>
                                </div>
<!--header-->
                                <!--content-->
                                <div class="content">
                                <div class="contact">
                                <div class="container">
                                <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                                <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                                <h2>Payment Details </h2>
                                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                <p>&nbsp;</p>
                                <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                                <table width="385"
height="133" border="0" align="center">
                                <tr>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Id</span></h3></td>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Food</span></h3></td>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Price</span></h3></td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php
while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
                                {
                                ?>
                                <tr>
                                <td><?php echo $row['id'];?></td>
                                <td><?php echo $row['fname'];?></td>
                                <td><?php echo $row['report'];
$total=$total+$row['report'];

```

```

                ?></td>
            </tr>

                <?php
                }
                ?>
            <tr>
            <td><span
class="style2"></span></td>
            <td><div align="center"
class="style2">
                <h3>Total Amount </h3>
            </div></td>
            <td><h3><span class="style2">$ <?php
echo $total;?></span>
                <label>
                <input type="hidden" name="t"
value="<?php echo $total;?>">
                </label>
            </h3></td>
            </tr>
                <tr>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td><label>
                    <input type="submit"
name="btn" value="Payment">
                </label></td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </form>
    <p>&nbsp;</p>
    <p>&nbsp;</p>
    <div class="contact-grids">
        <div class="clearfix"></div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
    <div class="footer-section">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="footer-grids">
                <div class="clearfix"></div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
<!--footer-->

</div>
<!--copy-->
    <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">

```

```

                <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
                </div>
            </div>
        <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>
USER PAYMENT
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);
$username=$_SESSION['un'];
        $total=0;
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from order_details where uname='$username' and
status=0");
if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$fit=$_REQUEST['t'];
header("Location:user_payment_1.php?f=".$fit);

}

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Good Food a Hotel and Restaurant Category Flat bootstrap
Responsive Website Template | Contact :: w3layouts</title>
<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all">
<link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css"
media="all" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Good Food Responsive web template,
Bootstrap Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web
template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia,
Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load",
function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function
hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<script src="js/jquery-1.11.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.js"></script>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Damion' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link
href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,300,300italic,40
0italic,600,600italic,700,700italic,800,800italic' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>

```

```

<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Ubuntu+Condensed'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style1 {color: #004080}
.style2 {color: #B35900}
-->
</style>
</head>
<body>
<!--header-->
    <div class="header head-top">
        <div class="container">
            <nav class="navbar navbar-default">
                <div class="container-fluid">
                    <!-- Brand and toggle get grouped for better mobile display
-->
                        <div class="navbar-header">
                            <button type="button" class="navbar-
toggle collapsed" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#bs-example-
navbar-collapse-1" aria-expanded="false">
                                <span class="sr-only">Toggle
navigation</span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                    <span class="icon-bar"></span>
                                </button>
                                <div class="navbar-brand">
                                    <h1><a
href="index.php">Hotel Billing</a></h1>
                                        </div>
                                    </div>
                                </div>
                    <!-- Collect the nav links, forms, and other content for
toggling -->
                        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse"
id="bs-example-navbar-collapse-1">
                            <ul class="nav navbar-nav">
                                <li ><a
href="user_home.php">Home <span class="sr-
only">(current)</span></a></li>
                                    <li ><a
href="user_order_food.php">Order Food</a></li>
                                    <li class="active"><a
href="user_payment.php">Payment</a></li>
                                    <li><a
href="index.php">Logout</a></li>
                                </ul>
                            </div><!-- /.navbar-collapse -->
                        </div><!-- /.container-fluid -->
                    </nav>

```

```

        </div>
    </div>
<!--header-->
    <!--content-->
        <div class="content">
            <div class="contact">
                <div class="container">
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>&nbsp;</h2>
                    <h2>Payment Details </h2>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <p>&nbsp;</p>
                    <form name="form1" method="post"
action="">
                        <table width="385"
height="133" border="0" align="center">
                            <tr>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Id</span></h3></td>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Food</span></h3></td>
                                <td><h3><span
class="style1">Price</span></h3></td>
                            </tr>
                                <?php
while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
                                {
                                    <tr>
                                        <td><?php echo $row['id'];?></td>
                                        <td><?php echo $row['fname'];?></td>
                                        <td><?php echo $row['report'];
$total=$total+$row['report'];
                                        <?></td>
                                    </tr>
                                        <?php
                                        }
                                        <tr>
                                            <td><span
class="style2"></span></td>
                                            <td><div align="center"
class="style2">
                                                <h3>Total Amount </h3>
                                            </div></td>

```

```

        <td><h3><span class="style2">$ <?php
echo $total;?></span>
        <label>
        <input type="hidden" name="t"
value="<?php echo $total;?>">
        </label>
        </h3></td>
</tr>
        <tr>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><label>
        <input type="submit"
name="btn" value="Payment">
        </label></td>
</tr>
</table>
        </form>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        <div class="contact-grids">
        <div class="clearfix"></div>
        </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
        <div class="footer-section">
        <div class="container">
        <div class="footer-grids">
        <div class="clearfix"></div>
        </div>
        </div>
        </div>
<!--footer-->
        </div>
        <!--copy-->
        <div class="copy-section">
        <div class="container">
        <p>&copy; 2020 Good Food. All
rights reserved | Design by Admin</p>
        </div>
        </div>
        <!--copy-->
</body>
</html>

```

9.2 SCREEN SHOTS:

Admin Login

username

password

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

localhost says
Successfully..

OK

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Processing request...

Add Food Details

Food Name
Type
Price
Image fff.JPG

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Food Details

Id	Food Name	Category	Quantity	Image
1	idly	Veg	50	

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Customer Details

Id	Name	Gender	Email Id	Mobile	Address
1	siva	Male	siva@gmail.com	9876543210	trichy

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Order Details

Id	User	Food	Food ID
1	siva	idly	1

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Payment Details

Id	User Name	Amount	Card	CCV	Ex.Date
1	siva	50	334234234	342	2020-01-23

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Customer Login

Name	<input type="text" value="siva"/>
Gender	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Male <input type="radio"/> Female
EmailId	<input type="text" value="siva@gmail.com"/>
MobileNumber	<input type="text" value="9876543210"/>
Address	<input type="text" value="trichy"/>
UserName	<input type="text" value="siva"/>
Password	<input type="password" value="..."/>
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>	

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

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Customer Login

Username	<input type="text" value="siva"/>
password	<input type="password" value="..."/>
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>	

New User Register Here....

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

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Food Details

Id	Food	Food ID	Price
1	idly	1	50

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Food Order

Id	Food Name	Category	Quantity	Image	Order
1	idly	Veg	50		select

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

localhost says
Product Add To Cart

OK

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Payment Details

Id	Food	Price
2	idly	50
Total Amount		\$ 50

Payment

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

References

1. Kamal Acharya. School management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
2. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
3. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
4. Kamal Acharya. Web chatting application project report management system. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
5. Kamal Acharya. RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>
6. Kamal Acharya. SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
7. Kamal Acharya. SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
8. Kamal Acharya. Online music portal management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
9. Kamal Acharya. COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
10. Kamal Acharya. AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
11. Kamal Acharya. Ludo management system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>
12. Kamal Acharya. Literature online quiz system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
13. Kamal Acharya. Avoid waste management system project. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
14. Kamal Acharya. CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
15. Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
16. Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
17. Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>

18. Acharya, Kamal, *POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
19. Acharya, Kamal, *Software testing for project report*. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
20. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT*. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
21. Acharya, Kamal, *Burger ordering system project report*. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
23. Acharya, Kamal, *Teachers Record Management System Project Report* (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>
23. Acharya, Kamal, *Dairy Management System Project Report* (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>
24. Acharya, Kamal, *Electrical Shop Management System Project* (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>
25. Acharya, Kamal, *Online book store management system project report*. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>
26. Acharya, Kamal, *Paint shop management system project report*. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
27. Acharya, Kamal, *Supermarket billing system project report*. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
28. Acharya, Kamal, *Online taxi booking system project report*. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
29. Acharya, Kamal, *Online car servicing system project report*. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
30. Acharya, Kamal, *School management system project report*. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>
31. Acharya, Kamal, *Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report* (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
32. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report* (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
33. Acharya, Kamal, *Fruit Shop Management System Project Report* (August 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
34. Acharya, Kamal, *Hall Booking Management System Project Report* (December 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
35. Acharya, Kamal, *Lundry Management System Project Report* (October 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>

36. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
37. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT* (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
38. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
39. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
40. Acharya, Kamal, *TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT* (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>
41. Acharya, Kamal, *Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report* (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>
42. Acharya, Kamal, *Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report* (April 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
43. Acharya, Kamal, *Automobile management system project report* (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
44. Acharya, Kamal, *College bus management system project report* (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
45. Acharya, Kamal, *Courier management system project report* (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>
46. Acharya, Kamal, *Event management system project report* (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>

47. Acharya, Kamal, *Library management system project report II* (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>